

SMARTSHOT

Wave-free supersonic pulsed gas jet system

The wave-free supersonic pulsed gas jet system SMARTSHOT™ is developed as a gas target for laser-plasma interaction studies such as laser-plasma acceleration, X-ray lasers, laser-plasma X-ray sources, etc. It can be used for the experimental studies which require the production of very localized high-density gas target with high repetition rate in vacuum.

◆ Density distribution of the gas jet

1. Wave-free supersonic slit nozzle (MS series)
2. High-speed solenoid valve (A2-6 series)
3. Fast pulsed valve driver (LX-03R)

(A2-6275-FL + MS05-10-120-1405)

(LX-03R)

◆ Characteristics of the system

1. The system uses a special slit nozzle to produce localized uniform gas jet in tiny region. It is designed by aerodynamic method and manufactured by micro-machining *.
2. The system uses a valve which can eject high-pressure gas (up to 7(10) MPa) through an orifice with large diameter. Accordingly, this can allow to use the slit nozzle with larger throat size and higher Mach number.
3. The valve can be operated with high-speed opening and closing (100-200 μ s) by proper driving pulse control. The valve can open fully and provide a stable ejection pressure even under the condition of regulation pressure of 10MPa **.
4. By the current output monitor signal from the LX-03R the gas jet operation can be precisely synchronized with laser pulses or signals from another devices. (In this case trigger pulse into LX-03R is required.)

* It has been applied for a patent in JAPAN (No.2004-100878)

** The ejection gas pressure reduction due to stroke shortening of an armature inside the solenoid valve can not occur even in high-pressure range at 10MPa. (we recommend up to 7MPa for normal use.)

High speed valve A2-6 series

The interferogram image of the gas jet by the wave-free supersonic slit jet shows a contour density map.

As shown in the interferogram image, the wave free nozzle can produce a supersonic laminar flow with sharp boundary between gas jet and Vacuum.

In contrast to sonic injection, an uniform density distribution is formed inside triangular area at the exit of the nozzle*.

(See red region in 3D-plot.)

* Reference J. D. Anderson, Jr, *Modern Compressible Flow with Historical Perspective 2nd Edition*, (Mc Graw Hill, 1989)

Time response of the gas jet

Wave-free supersonic nozzle MS series

We can design the nozzle based on your requirements, such as density and species of gas, target size (L x W), Mach number of the flow, available gas pressure etc.

Sample Pictures (MS05-10-166)

Sample;
 Stagnant pressure vs. Density
 @ exit of the nozzle
 Mach number = 5
 (a) for helium gas
 (b) for N2 gas

◆ High speed valve A2-6 series

> Valve Type	A2-6443
> Orifice (D) [mm]	φ1.5
> Operation Range [MPa]	0.01 - 7(10)
> Remarks	low leakage (Soft poppet)
> Gas temperature	-10 - 40°C (No freeze)

◆ Specification

1) LX-03R Fast Solenoid Valve Driver

Input Voltage	85 - 264V (AC)
Drive voltage	40 - 180V (Pulse)
Pulse duration for excitation	0.1-9.9ms
Pulse duration for negative voltage	0.1-10.1ms
Maximum Drive current	35A

2) A2-6443 Fast Solenoid Valve

Out-let Aperture size	D=1.5 mm
Maximum working pressure	7MPa
Internal leakage	Less than 10 cm ³ /min
External leakage	Less than 1.33*10 ⁻⁶ Pa*m ³ /s He
Voltage	DC48V for driving armature (7~10 ms), DC12V for keeping armature position (0~10 ms)
Gas Connection	1/4 inch Swagelok
Repetition	10Hz (Max)

3) MS05-XX-166 Wave-free slit nozzles

Nozzle Wall	designed by the Method of Characteristics
Exit slit size	(1.2x XXmm)
Throat width	120 micron with slit shape
Pulse duration for negative voltage	0.1-10.1ms
Mach Number at Exit of nozzle	~5 (for Helium, Argon)

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